

Simplified Interaction Formulae and their Accuracy in Hollow Sections

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ABSTRACT

Hollow sections are the preferred solution in those cases where architectural requirements are a priority. For hollow sections, it is possible to carry out both elastic and plastic verification of the cross-sectional load-bearing capacity. Classification in cross-sectional classes 1 or 2 means that the plastic load bearing capacity can be utilized. This presents both ecological and economic advantages. In technical standards and the literature, a wide variety of interaction formulae can be found. In most cases, the accuracy for these solutions is not provided. In this article, the accuracy of the different interaction formulae for frequently used combinations of internal forces and moments is determined using an optimization approach. Focus of this research is on the accuracy of the interaction formulae provided in EN 1993-1-1 and further approaches from specialized literature. In addition to the comparison of the different accuracy levels, simplified interaction formulae will be introduced here allowing conservative plastic design of hollow sections.

Keywords: plastic load-bearing capacity, interaction formulae, hollow section, simplification

1 INTRODUCTION

In steel construction, alongside doubly symmetric I-sections, hollow sections are also used. These hollow sections are categorized by their cross-section as circular, square or rectangular. This study involves the investigation of square and rectangular hollow sections (see *Fig. 1*).

Fig. 1. Hollow sections

The verification of sufficient cross-sectional load-bearing capacity can be carried out using elastic or plastic approaches. A prerequisite for the determination of the plastic load-bearing capacity is the classification of a section into cross-sectional class 1 or 2. On account of the higher load-bearing capacity of a plastic design and for reasons of sustainability, plastic cross-sectional verification is preferred. An overview of commonly used methods for the determination of the plastic load-bearing capacity is given in *Table 1*, where a broad distinction is made between manual calculations and numerical methods.

Table 1. Typical methods for the determination of the plastic load-bearing capacity, (1)

	Method	Application in
Manual calculations	Plastic neutral axis approach	Baptista (2), Horne (3), Rubin (4), (5), Neal (6)
	Partial internal force method (PIM)	Kindmann/Frickel (7), (8)
	Extended partial internal force method (PIM-plus)	Kindmann/Ludwig (9), (10), (11)
Numerical methods	Strain iteration method	Software INCA 2 (12)
		Osterrieder/Werner/Kretzschmar (13),
	Optimization method	Osterrieder/Kretzschmar (14) Software LILOBEC (15)

In (1) and in (16), the accuracy of the plastic load-bearing capacity of doubly symmetric I-sections is investigated. In addition, these studies also introduce simplified interaction formulae for such sections.

2 OBJECTIVES

The motivation for the following investigation can be summarized as follows:

- Determination of the accuracy of the N - M_y - M_z interaction formulae for square and rectangular hollow sections
- An overview of the number of input parameters in each interaction formula
- Introduction of a simplified N - M_y - M_z interaction formula with the minimum possible number of input parameters

The newly introduced simplified interaction formula should take the internal forces and moments N , M_y and M_z into account (see Fig. 2). At the same time, in the event that one of these is equal to zero, it should be possible to derive a plausible verification equation for the available internal forces and moments. This approach will be illustrated using the newly introduced solution in Fig. 2 and in Table 9. The logical structure of the verification equation is of particular importance to the user in order to avoid "jumps" in the load during verification. It is common in the literature for interaction formulae to be stated for two internal forces or moments. These formulae cannot, however, be derived directly from interaction formulae for three internal forces and moments, and so, this often leads to confusion.

Fig. 2. Logical structure of the newly introduced interaction equation for the case where one internal force or moment is equal to zero

rectangular hollow section (RHS) $\left(\frac{1}{1-1.1 \cdot n^{1.8}} \cdot \frac{M_y}{M_{pl,y}} \right)^{1.8 \cdot \left(1 + \frac{n}{2}\right)} + \left(\frac{1}{1-1.1 \cdot n^{1.4}} \cdot \frac{M_z}{M_{pl,z}} \right)^{1.4 \cdot \left(1 + \frac{n}{2}\right)} \leq 1$		
$N-M_y (M_z = 0)$	$N-M_z (M_y = 0)$	$M_y-M_z (N = 0)$
$1.1 \cdot \left(\frac{N}{N_{pl}} \right)^{1.8} + \frac{M_y}{M_{pl,y}} \leq 1$	$1.1 \cdot \left(\frac{N}{N_{pl}} \right)^{1.4} + \frac{M_z}{M_{pl,z}} \leq 1$	$\left(\frac{M_y}{M_{pl,y}} \right)^{1.8} + \left(\frac{M_z}{M_{pl,z}} \right)^{1.4} \leq 1$
where $n = N/N_{pl} \leq 0.9$; apply positive internal forces and moments (absolute values)		

Fig. 2.(Continued) Logical structure of the newly introduced interaction equation for the case where one internal force or moment is equal to zero

3 PLASTIC ULTIMATE INTERNAL FORCES AND MOMENTS

The plastic ultimate internal forces and moments for hollow sections can be found in established engineering tables, e. g. (17). In these, the fillets of hollow sections are, in part, considered in a highly simplified manner. This leads to deviations during the determination of plastic ultimate internal forces and moments. In this study, hot-formed hollow sections are considered in accordance with EN 10210-2 (18) while cold-formed hollow sections follow EN 10219-2 (19). The description of their geometry is presented in Fig. 3. The plastic ultimate internal forces and moments in this study have been determined according to Table 2. The formulae present a simplification of the equations found in (8) and have also been applied in (20). As an alternative to Table 2, the plastic ultimate internal forces and moments can also be taken from (17), for example.

Fig. 3. Dimensions of the cross-sectional shapes of a) hot and b) cold-formed hollow sections

Table 2. Plastic ultimate internal force N_{pl} and moments $M_{pl,y}$ and $M_{pl,z}$ (8) and (20)

$N_{pl} = \left[2 \cdot t \cdot (b + h - 2 \cdot t) - (4 - \pi) \cdot (r_o^2 - r_i^2) \right] \cdot f_y$
$M_{pl,y} = \left[\frac{b \cdot h^2}{4} - \frac{(b - 2 \cdot t) \cdot (h - 2 \cdot t)^2}{4} \right] \cdot f_y - 0.8584 \cdot \left[r_o^2 \cdot \left(\frac{h}{2} - 0.2234 \cdot r_o \right) - r_i^2 \cdot \left(\frac{h}{2} - t - 0.2234 \cdot r_i \right) \right] \cdot f_y$
$M_{pl,z} = \left[\frac{h \cdot b^2}{4} - \frac{(h - 2 \cdot t) \cdot (b - 2 \cdot t)^2}{4} \right] \cdot f_y - 0.8584 \cdot \left[r_o^2 \cdot \left(\frac{b}{2} - 0.2234 \cdot r_o \right) - r_i^2 \cdot \left(\frac{b}{2} - t - 0.2234 \cdot r_i \right) \right] \cdot f_y$

4 INTERACTION FORMULAE FOR N, M_Y AND M_Z

4.1 Preliminary remarks

For the investigations presented below, the following boundary conditions apply:

- Cross-sectional class 1 or 2 is required.
- Fillets are taken into account (see Fig. 3).
- A bilinear stress-strain relationship without strain-hardening is assumed.
- Plastic ultimate internal forces and moments are determined according to Table 2.
- Interaction formulae from the literature are mostly applied in their original form. In general, absolute values for the individual internal forces and moments are used here.

As part of this parametric investigation, square and rectangular hollow profiles from the following standards have been taken into account: EN 10210-2 (hot-formed) (18) and EN 10219-2 (cold-formed) (19). The list has subsequently been extended to a number of hollow sections which are practical for the construction industry, and not part of the standards given above. In total, for the interaction formula N-M_y-M_z, 574 hollow sections with 526 combinations of internal forces and moments have been investigated. This results in 301,924 combinations investigated for each interaction formula. The ultimate load for combination N-M_y-M_z was also determined by means of LILOBEC (15). In the determination of the deviations, all internal forces and moments are considered along with the same load factor α_{load} . Further details regarding the LILOBEC program (15) can be found in (21).

4.2 Overview of the analyzed interaction formulae

In Table 3 an overview of the analyzed interaction formulae for N-M_y-M_z can be found. In this list, the only solutions to be investigated are those in which all three internal forces and moments are considered. In order to provide an initial impression of the various interaction formulae, the necessary parameters and the number of cases are listed. The solutions in Table 3 are sorted by the number of parameters as the first priority. At this point, attention must be drawn to the fact that in (20), both detailed and simplified solutions are presented for the N-M_y-M_z combination of internal forces and moments. In the following, these will be differentiated as (20) (detailed) and (20) (simple).

Table 3. Number of parameters, cases and equations for individual interaction formulae

Reference	Verific. in	Num. para.	Parameters	Num. cases
Kind./Jon./Kno. (20) (detailed)	Table 4	9	b, h, t, α , β_b , β_h , N _{pl} , M _{pl,y} , M _{pl,z}	5
Kind./Kraus/Nieb. (17)	Table 5	7	b, t, h, r _o , N _{pl} , M _{pl,y} , M _{pl,z}	4
EN 1993-1-1 (22)	Table 6	7	A, b, t, h, N _{pl} , M _{pl,y} , M _{pl,z}	3
Rubin (5)	Table 7	6	A, h, t, N _{pl} , M _{pl,y} , M _{pl,z}	7
Vayas (23)	Table 8	6	A, b, t, N _{pl} , M _{pl,y} , M _{pl,z}	5
Ludwig (Fig. 2)	Table 9	4	SHS or RHS, N _{pl} , M _{pl,y} , M _{pl,z}	2
Kind./Jon./Kno. (20) (simple)	Table 10	3	N _{pl} , M _{pl,y} , M _{pl,z}	1

A large number of the necessary parameters can be taken from engineering tables. Often, they concern plastic ultimate internal forces and moments in accordance with Table 2 or geometrical values from Fig. 3. Solution (20) (detailed) is an exception here. The values of α , β_b and β_h must be taken directly from (20). In the following, the interaction formulae will be listed in Table 4 through to Table 10. In general, absolute values for the individual internal forces and moments are used here. It is clear from Table 4 to Table 10 that the effort required for verification using the various interaction formulae differs greatly.

Table 4. Interaction formulae N-M_y-M_z according to Kindmann/Jonczyk/Knobloch (20) (detailed)

Case I: $0 \leq \frac{N}{2} + \frac{M_z}{a_w} \leq N_{pl,w}$	$M_y \leq M_{pl,y} - \frac{N^2 + 4 \cdot (M_z/a_w)^2}{8 \cdot t \cdot f_y}$
Case II: $0 \leq \frac{N}{2} + \frac{M_y}{a_f} \leq N_{pl,f}$	$M_z \leq M_{pl,z} - \frac{N^2 + 4 \cdot (M_y/a_f)^2}{8 \cdot t \cdot f_y}$
Case III: if cases I, II, IV and V are not definitive	$M_y \leq \frac{M_{pl,y}}{2} - \frac{N_o}{2} \cdot a_f - \frac{(N - N_{pl}/2 - N_o)^2}{4 \cdot t \cdot f_y}$
where $q = 4 \cdot t \cdot f_y \cdot [M_z - (N_{pl} - N_{pl,f} - N) \cdot a_w/2 - N_{pl,f} \cdot b_f/4]$ and $N_o = t \cdot f_y \cdot a_w - \sqrt{(t \cdot f_y \cdot a_w)^2 - q}$	
Case IV: $2 \cdot N_{pl,w} \leq N \leq N_{pl}$ and $M_y \geq (N_{pl} - N) \cdot \frac{a_f}{2}$	$M_y \leq (N_{pl} - N) \cdot \left(\frac{a_f + t}{2} - \frac{N_{pl} - N}{4 \cdot b_f \cdot f_y} \right) - M_z \cdot \frac{t}{b_f}$
Case V: $2 \cdot N_{pl,f} \leq N \leq N_{pl}$ and $M_z \geq (N_{pl} - N) \cdot \frac{a_w}{2}$	$M_z \leq (N_{pl} - N) \cdot \left(\frac{a_w + t}{2} - \frac{N_{pl} - N}{4 \cdot h_w \cdot f_y} \right) - M_y \cdot \frac{t}{h_w}$
where $b_m = b - t$; $h_m = h - t$; $a_w = b_m - \beta_b \cdot t$; $a_f = h_m - \beta_h \cdot t$; $b_f = b_m - \alpha \cdot t$; $h_w = h_m - \alpha \cdot t$ $N_{pl,w} = t \cdot h_w \cdot f_y$; $N_{pl,f} = t \cdot b_f \cdot f_y$; Values of α , β_b and β_h (see (20))	

Table 5. Interaction formulae N-M_y-M_z according to Kindmann/Kraus/Niebuhr (17)

$(M_y/M_{N,y})^{1.6} + (M_z/M_{N,z})^{1.6} \leq 1$ where	
Case I (N-M _y): $0 \leq N \leq 2 \cdot t \cdot (h - 2 \cdot t) \cdot f_y$	$M_{y,N} \leq M_{pl,y} - N^2 / (8 \cdot t \cdot f_y)$
Case II (N-M _y): $2 \cdot t \cdot (h - 2 \cdot t) \cdot f_y < N \leq N_{pl}$	$M_{y,N} \leq (N_{pl} - N) \cdot \left(\frac{h}{2} - \frac{N_{pl} - N}{4 \cdot (b - 1.2 \cdot r_o) \cdot f_y} \right)$
Case I (N-M _z): $0 \leq N \leq 2 \cdot t \cdot (b - 2 \cdot t) \cdot f_y$	$M_{z,N} \leq M_{pl,z} - N^2 / (8 \cdot t \cdot f_y)$
Case II (N-M _z): $2 \cdot t \cdot (b - 2 \cdot t) \cdot f_y < N \leq N_{pl}$	$M_{z,N} \leq (N_{pl} - N) \cdot \left(\frac{b}{2} - \frac{N_{pl} - N}{4 \cdot (h - 1.2 \cdot r_o) \cdot f_y} \right)$

Table 6. Interaction formulae N-M_y-M_z according to EN 1993-1-1 (22)

$\left(\frac{1}{\min\left(\frac{1-n}{1-0.5 \cdot a_w}; 1\right)} \cdot \frac{M_y}{M_{pl,y}} \right)^{\min\left(\frac{1.66}{1-1.13 \cdot n^2}; 6.0\right)} + \left(\frac{1}{\min\left(\frac{1-n}{1-0.5 \cdot a_f}; 1\right)} \cdot \frac{M_z}{M_{pl,z}} \right)^{\min\left(\frac{1.66}{1-1.13 \cdot n^2}; 6.0\right)} \leq 1$	
where $n = N/N_{pl}$; $a_w = (A - 2 \cdot b \cdot t)/A \leq 0.5$; $a_f = (A - 2 \cdot h \cdot t)/A \leq 0.5$	

Table 7. Interaction formulae N-M_y-M_z according to Rubin (5) (Original layout)

$0 \leq n \leq \delta$	$\delta \leq n \leq 1-\delta$	$1-\delta \leq n \leq 1$
$0 \leq m_y \leq m_1$		$0 \leq m_y \leq m_2$
$m_z \leq 1 - \left(n^2 + \left(\frac{2-\delta}{2} \cdot m_y \right)^2 \right) / (1-\delta^2)$		$m_z \leq 2 \cdot \frac{1-n}{1+\delta}$
$m_1 \leq m_y \leq m_3$	$m_1 \leq m_y \leq m_4$	$m_2 \leq m_y \leq m_4$
$m_z \leq 2 \cdot \frac{(1-\delta) \cdot (1-n) - \left[1-n - \sqrt{\delta \left(1-n - \frac{2-\delta}{2} \cdot m_y \right)^2} \right]^2}{1-\delta^2}$		
$m_3 \leq m_y \leq m_5$	$m_1 = 2 - 2 \cdot \frac{1+n}{2-\delta} \quad m_2 = \frac{\delta}{2 \cdot (2-\delta)} \cdot \left[1 - \left(1 - 2 \cdot \frac{1-n}{\delta} \right)^2 \right]$	
$m_z \leq \frac{2 \cdot \sqrt{\delta \cdot (2-\delta) \cdot (1-m_y)} - n^2}{1+\delta}$	$m_3 = 1 - \frac{n^2 + (\delta-n)^2}{\delta \cdot (2-\delta)} \quad m_4 = 2 \cdot \frac{1-n}{2-\delta} \quad m_5 = 1 - \frac{n^2}{\delta \cdot (2-\delta)}$	
where $n = N/N_{pl}$; $m_y = M_y/M_{pl,y}$; $m_z = M_z/M_{pl,z}$; $\delta = 2 \cdot (h-t)/A$		

Table 8. Interaction formulae N-M_y-M_z according to Vayas (23)

Case I	
$\frac{m_y \cdot (1+\alpha_f)}{2 \cdot \alpha_f} \geq \frac{m_z \cdot (1+\alpha_w)}{2 \cdot \alpha_w}$ and $\frac{n}{\alpha_w} + \frac{m_z \cdot (1+\alpha_w)}{2 \cdot \alpha_w} \leq 1$: $\frac{m_y \cdot (1+\alpha_f) - \alpha_w + \frac{[0.5 \cdot m_z \cdot (1+\alpha_w)]^2 + n^2}{\alpha_w}}{2 \cdot \alpha_f} \leq 1$	
Case II	
$\frac{m_y \cdot (1+\alpha_f)}{2 \cdot \alpha_f} < \frac{m_z \cdot (1+\alpha_w)}{2 \cdot \alpha_w}$ and $\frac{n}{\alpha_f} + \frac{m_y \cdot (1+\alpha_f)}{2 \cdot \alpha_f} \leq 1$: $\frac{m_z \cdot (1+\alpha_w) - \alpha_f + \frac{[0.5 \cdot m_y \cdot (1+\alpha_f)]^2 + n^2}{\alpha_f}}{2 \cdot \alpha_w} \leq 1$	
Case III	
$m_y \geq \frac{1-n-(1-n)^2/\alpha_w}{0.5 \cdot (1+\alpha_f)}$ and $m_z \geq \frac{1-n-(1-n)^2/\alpha_f}{0.5 \cdot (1+\alpha_w)}$: $m_y \leq \frac{1-n}{0.5 \cdot (1+\alpha_f)}$ and $m_z \leq \frac{1-n}{0.5 \cdot (1+\alpha_w)}$	
and $n + \alpha_w \cdot \sqrt{1 - [n - \alpha_f + 0.5 \cdot m_y \cdot (1+\alpha_f)]/\alpha_w} + \alpha_f \cdot \sqrt{1 - [n - \alpha_w + 0.5 \cdot m_z \cdot (1+\alpha_w)]/\alpha_f} \geq 1$	
Case IV	Case V
$m_y \leq \frac{1-n-(1-n)^2/\alpha_w}{0.5 \cdot (1+\alpha_f)}$; $m_z \leq \frac{1-n}{0.5 \cdot (1+\alpha_w)}$	$m_z \leq \frac{1-n-(1-n)^2/\alpha_f}{0.5 \cdot (1+\alpha_w)}$; $m_y \leq \frac{1-n}{0.5 \cdot (1+\alpha_f)}$
where $n = N/N_{pl}$; $m_y = M_y/M_{pl,y}$; $m_z = M_z/M_{pl,z}$; $\alpha_f = 2 \cdot (b-t)/A$; $\alpha_w = 1-\alpha_f$	

Table 9. Interaction formulae N-M_y-M_z according to Ludwig

square hollow section (SHS)	$\left(\frac{1}{1-1.1 \cdot n^{1.7}} \cdot \frac{M_y}{M_{pl,y}} \right)^{1.7 \cdot \left(1 + \frac{n}{2}\right)} + \left(\frac{1}{1-1.1 \cdot n^{1.7}} \cdot \frac{M_z}{M_{pl,z}} \right)^{1.7 \cdot \left(1 + \frac{n}{2}\right)} \leq 1$ where $n = N/N_{pl} \leq 0.9$
rectangular hollow section (RHS)	$\left(\frac{1}{1-1.1 \cdot n^{1.8}} \cdot \frac{M_y}{M_{pl,y}} \right)^{1.8 \cdot \left(1 + \frac{n}{2}\right)} + \left(\frac{1}{1-1.1 \cdot n^{1.4}} \cdot \frac{M_z}{M_{pl,z}} \right)^{1.4 \cdot \left(1 + \frac{n}{2}\right)} \leq 1$ where $n = N/N_{pl} \leq 0.9$

Table 10. Interaction formulae N-M_y-M_z according to Kindmann/Jonczyk/Knobloch (20) (simple)

	$\left(\frac{1}{1-n^{1.4}} \cdot \frac{M_y}{M_{pl,y}} \right)^{1.64 + \frac{n+n^2}{2}} + \left(\frac{1}{1-n^{1.3}} \cdot \frac{M_z}{M_{pl,z}} \right)^{1.64 + \frac{n+n^2}{2}} \leq 1$ where $n = N/N_{pl}$
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4.3 Accuracy

According to Table 3, seven different verification options are available to the user. Alongside the scope of the verification process, the accuracy of the verification equations is a decisive factor in selecting a preferred verification format. In Fig. 4, the deviations of the interaction formulae from Table 4 to Table 10 are summarized. The load factor, α_{load} , is shown on the horizontal axis. The results for $\alpha_{load} = 1$ are based on LILOBEC (15). All internal forces and moments considered here are multiplied by this factor. A factor of $\alpha_{load} > 1$ thus results in a non-conservative design. In addition to this accuracy (on the horizontal axis), the number of required input parameters for the verification process (e.g. b, t, N_{pl}, etc.) is shown on the vertical axis.

Fig. 4. Deviations in the interaction formulae selected for N, M_y and M_z dependent upon the number of input parameters

It is clear that for very precise verification following Kindmann/Jonczyk/Knobloch (20) (detailed), a greater number of input parameters are required. In addition to this, 3 input parameters found in Kind-

mann/Jonczyk/Knobloch (20) (α , β_b and β_h) are not found in the established engineering tables. Despite having 7 input parameters, the interaction formula following EN 1993-1-1 (22) exhibits the greatest deviation of up to 7.2 % on the non-conservative side. If the main priority is a conservative design ($\alpha_{load} \leq 1.005$), the solutions given by Kindmann/Kraus/Niebuhr (17), Ludwig (Fig. 2) and Kindmann/Jonczyk/Knobloch (20) (simple) are preferable. The aim of this study is to identify a simple and conservative interaction formula with the least possible number of input parameters. Taking Table 3 and Fig. 4 into consideration, the interaction formulae from Ludwig (Fig. 2) and Kindmann/Jonczyk/Knobloch (20) (simple) will be further investigated. The scatter of the solutions is presented in Fig. 5. For comparison, the solution from EN 1993-1-1 (22) has also been included. The factors in Fig. 5 result from the comparison of the selected interaction condition to the simple linear interaction given in Fig. 5. As a rule, the linear interaction is very conservative, and thus most of the factors are located above 1. For the determination of the factors in Fig. 5 (left), the conditions found in Fig. 5 (right) apply. Fig. 5 makes it clear that the interaction formulae from Ludwig (Fig. 2) shows a smaller scattering and simultaneously leads to more economic results compared to the solution from Kindmann/Jonczyk/Knobloch (20) (simple).

Fig. 5. Deviations in the selected interaction formulae selected for N , M_y and M_z according to Table 6, Table 9 and Table 10

5 EXAMPLE

In Fig. 6, the interaction curves for a square hollow section - 120x6.3-S235 (cold formed) are shown. The proportion of the normal force is $N/N_{pl} = 0.2$. In this case, the interaction formulae from Ludwig (Fig. 2) and Kindmann/Kraus/Niebuhr (17) lead to the best results. In Fig. 6, the maximum moments M_y are also shown for the case where $N/N_{pl} = 0.2$ and $M_z/M_{pl,z} = 0.6$. In this example, it is essential to note that only the internal moment M_y is varied. In contrast, all of the internal forces and moments are varied in the determination of the factor α_{load} in Fig. 4. The consideration of all internal forces and moments is regarded as being more significant.

Square hollow section (SHS)
120x6.3-S235 (cold formed)

Example

$$N = 128 \text{ kN } (N/N_{pl} = 0.2)$$

$$M_z = 1610 \text{ kNcm } (M_z/M_{pl,z} = 0.6)$$

$$M_y \text{ (Table 6)} = 1978 \text{ kNcm (EN 1993-1-1, (22))}$$

$$M_y = 1849 \text{ kNcm (LILOBEC, (15))}$$

$$M_y \text{ (Table 9)} = 1823 \text{ kNcm (Ludwig, Fig. 2)}$$

$$M_y \text{ (Table 5)} = 1688 \text{ kNcm (Kind./Kra/Nie, (17))}$$

$$M_y \text{ (Table 10)} = 1594 \text{ kNcm (Kind./Jon./Kno, (20)) (simple)}$$

Fig. 6. Deviations in the interaction formulae selected for N , M_y and M_z according to Table 6, Table 9 and Table 10 for square hollow section 120x6.3-S235 (cold formed)

6 CONCLUSIONS

The information in Table 3 provides the user with an initial step to be able to estimate the effort required for the verification process for an N - M_y - M_z interaction. The evaluation of the accuracy in Fig. 4 makes clear the deviations in the individual interaction formulae. Consequently, the user can decide for themselves which interaction formula they prefer. A further aim of this study was to introduce an easily applicable interaction formula. Using the interaction formulae from Ludwig in Fig. 2 or Table 9, a very simple and simultaneously conservative design for square or rectangular hollow sections is possible. In Table 11, a greatly simplified overview is provided as a decision-making tool.

Table 11. Simplified overview of the accuracy and user-friendliness of the interaction formulae investigated

Reference	Kind./Jon./ Kno. (20) (detailed)	Ludwig (Fig. 2)	Kind./Jon./ Kno. (20) (simple)	EN 1993-1-1 (22)	Kind./Kra./ Nie. (17)	Rubin (5)	Vayas (23)
Accuracy	++	+	○	-	+	-	○
Simplicity	-	++	++	+	○	-	-

Legend: ++ very good; + good, ○ satisfactory, - adequate

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